

NONLINEAR BEHAVIOUR ANALYSIS DURING INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TEST OF THE COMPOSITE LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

Some influence that may cause nonlinear behaviour and affect the characterization of interlaminar fracture toughness of the typical DCB, ENF and EDT tests of GL/BMI, GR/BMI composite laminates with and without interleaved adhesive layer is studied. The modified data-reduction methods and test procedures are presented and discussed .

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, mode I , mode II and mixed-mode delamination fracture toughnesses become important parameters to characterize material properties and are used to predict delamination onset. While the brittle matrix composites are modified to be more ductile and many kinds of toughened matrices are used [1]. Hence , nonlinear behaviour is often reported and is still an obscured problem during interlaminar fracture toughness test and data reduction [2-5]. Generally, nonlinearity includes material nonlinearity and geometrical nonlinearity. However, other effects such as fiber bridging and microcracks will also cause nonlinearity, these effects should be eliminated since our aim is to get the real delamination fracture toughness. So this paper tries to analyze and discuss some influence which may cause nonlinearity and affect fracture toughness and data-reduction.

2. EXPERIMENTS

Two kinds of material systems were tested . They were T300/QY8911, GR/BMI composites and S2/QY8911 GL/BMI composites. Double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notch flexure (ENF) specimens [1] were cut from unidirectional panels $[0_{24}]_T$ that contain Teflon film and are with and without interleaved adhesive . Edge delamination test (EDT) [6] specimens were cut into rectangular laminates from multidirectional panels whose layups were $[\pm 45 / 0 / 90]_S$, $[\pm 30_2 / 90]_S$, $[\pm 30_2 / 90 / 90]_S$. All the tests were carried out using a MTS 880 machine under displacement control. Both EDT and DCB specimens were step loaded and unloaded to obtain the detail loading-deformation curves. It was found that the stress-strain curve of the GFRP EDT specimen had slight nonlinearity so the damaged laminate stiffness was given the value of the average tangent stiffness close to the origin. As soon as delamination initiated , specimen was unloaded to record the laminate stiffness because this value was proposed to be used in the new

data– reduction method to eliminate the influence of matrix cracking. Detail test procedures and results will be reported in[7].

3. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the energy balance principle of fracture mechanics, the energy release rate G_c of a main crack under constant quasi–static loading P can be obtained from

$$G_c dA_c + G_d dA_d = dW - dU_e - dU_p \quad (1)$$

where W is the work done by the external forces. U_e, U_p are the elastic strain energy and plastic strain energy respectively, A_c, A_d are the main crack surface and the surface of other microcracks or damage. Hence, the contribution of the fracture energy by other microcracks or damage should be eliminated in order to characterize the energy release rate of the main crack accurately if more than one crack exists in the cracked body.

On the nonlinear fracture toughness, Liebowitz employed the macroscopic empirical method on the global load–displacement curve, his result was included in the effects of not only elastic response but also inelastic response such as plastic deformation and subcritical crack etc[8]. So his method mainly deals with the significant material nonlinearity not other effects that only cause weak nonlinear $P-\delta$ behaviour. Generally, the nonlinear fracture toughness can be expressed by a correction coefficient β form[8]

$$G_c^{NL} = (1 + \beta)G_c \quad (2)$$

where G_c is the linear fracture toughness. Liebowitz’s method can’t distinguish other influence such as microcracks that affect the characterization of fracture toughness of the main crack. For instance, the improved fracture toughness of the interleaved laminate with adhesive layer should be the contribution of the modified interface between interleaf and composites, not the microcracks in the interleaved adhesive layer. So here we try to analyze some kinds of detail effects that should not be included in the real fracture toughness, sometimes these effects may cause nonlinear load–deformation behaviour.

3.1. Mode I DCB Test The fracture toughness of the DCB specimen can be expressed by the classical beam analysis in two forms[1]:

$$G_{Ic}^a = \frac{P^2 a^2}{2bE_{11}I} \quad (a) \quad G_{Ic}^b = \frac{3P\delta}{2ab} \quad (b) \quad (3)$$

where b is the half specimen width and δ is the crack open displacement, $E_{11}I$ is the flexure stiffness of the beam. When large deflection appears in the DCB test, the effective crack length a_{eff} should be used instead of the natural crack length a in data reduction using eq.(3a). But the former large deflection analysis is very complex in practical use. Here we try to get the simple empirical form of large deflection correction by extending Williams’s works[3]. From large deflection analysis of the linear beam, we have:

$$F_a = \frac{a_{eff}}{a} = \frac{2\sqrt{\sin\alpha}}{I_1} \quad \frac{\delta}{a} = \frac{2I_2}{I_1} \quad (4)$$

where α, I_1, I_2 are the end slope of the cantilever, and two elliptic integrals defined in[3]. We find these parameters are all independent of the load and structure of the cantilever beam, that means as long as one parameter of the beam such as α or δ/a is determined, the beam shape and then other parameters can be obtained so the crack length correction factor F_a is only a geometrical relation function of the δ/a . Hence, it can be approximated by a polynomial instead of the complex calculation of elliptic integral and

interpolation . We employ such a polynomial to get the effective crack length and then the correction factor of the fracture toughness from eq.(3a):

$$F_a(\delta/a) \approx 1.016 - 0.1344(\delta/a) + 0.104(\delta/a)^2 - 0.148(\delta/a)^3 \quad (5)$$

$$F_G = \frac{G_{IC}^{NL}}{G_{IC}^a} = (F_a(\delta/a))^2 \quad (6)$$

The comparison of the approximate and exact correction factors of the fracture toughness is shown in Fig.1, good agreement is found. Another simple form of the correction factor of fracture toughness can be used also:

$$F_G(\delta/a) \approx 0.986 + 0.0947(\delta/a) - 0.457(\delta/a)^2 + 0.063(\delta/a)^3 \quad (7)$$

Let's analyze the deviations of eq.(3a) and (3b):

$$\frac{dG_{IC}^a}{G_{IC}^a} = 2\frac{da}{a} \quad \frac{dG_{IC}^b}{G_{IC}^b} = -\frac{da}{a} \quad (8)$$

We know that the difference between effective and natural crack lengths da induced by the large deflection will lead to smaller error on fracture toughness using eq.(3b) without large deflection correction . Hence, if the deflection is not very large ,Berry's method in a form like eq.(3b) is still applicable. Similar result was also gotten in [9].

As reported in other literature, G_{IC} increases with the crack propagation [1,10], the main contribution results from the fiber bridging in DCB specimen. In experiment, we observed that the fiber bridging was very serious and it led to a "damage zone" near the crack tip and then caused weak nonlinear $P-\delta$ behaviour especially in GFRP specimen. This results in a large G_{IC} value which overestimates the real mode I fracture toughness greatly, as shown in Fig.2, the difference of G_{IC} values of the GFRP DCB at initial short and long crack lengths is more than 100% . It seems that the GFRP specimen has more serious fiber bridging[10], that may result from the relatively bigger fiber diameter and the rough surface of the prepreg of the GFRP composites. Hence, how to eliminate these effects needs further investigation because in mixed-mode test , for instance, the edge delamination test, no fiber bridging is observed. The modified method is to only use the data at short crack length or eliminate the fiber bridging during test[10].

3.2. Mode II ENF Test According to beam analysis, shear deformation effect to the mode II fracture toughness is within 2 % for the present thin CFRP and GFRP beams and can be neglected. On the large deflection correction of the ENF specimen, Williams got a correction factor to express the fracture toughness with geometrical nonlinearity.

$$G_{IIc}^{NL} = G_{IIc} F_{ENF} \quad F_{ENF} = 1 - k\left(\frac{\delta}{L}\right)^2 \quad (9)$$

where G_{IIc} is the fracture toughness obtained from the classical linear beam theory .

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{36a^2 \delta^2 E_{11} h^3}{(2L^3 + 3a^3)^2} \quad (10)$$

where h is the half thickness of the specimen, $2L$ is the span of the test beam. Using these equations, we may obtain the magnitude of the large deflection correction of the typical thin ENF specimen with $2L=100$ mm, $a=0.5L$. The possible G_{IIc} varies from 100-3000 J/m^2 which is within the former measured values [1]. The variance of the correction factor has been shown in Fig.3 , and the flexure stiffness of the beam is also within the

possible range. We learn that the correction of large deflection of the typical ENF specimen is not more than 3% and it can be neglected for either thermoset matrix composites with and without interleaf or thermoplastic matrix composites. Similar result has been found by Mall using finite element analysis[11].

While the macroscopic nonlinear P- δ curves were often observed either in our interleaved ENF specimen or in thermoplastic matrix composite ENF specimen[2], regular shear microcracks were observed in the interleaved adhesive layer when the nonlinear P- δ relation appeared[7]. Liebowitz's nonlinear fracture toughness can be gotten by using the empirical method, a 20% or so nonlinear correction coefficient is found[2,7]. The nonlinear fracture toughness results from the so called material nonlinearity including the effects of plastic deformation and subcritical cracks[8], but we can not distinguish which part of the fracture toughness is the contribution of the microcracks. Let's see the basic equation (1), the effect of microcracks or damage shouldn't be included in the fracture toughness. Further works should be done because although we can obtain a global nonlinear fracture toughness value, it overestimates the real fracture toughness.

3.3. Mixed-Mode EDT Test Edge delamination test is now often used to measure the mixed-mode interlaminar fracture toughness. Based on the laminate stiffness analysis, O'Brien obtained the mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness as following[6]:

$$G_c = \frac{\varepsilon^2 t}{2} (E_x^0 - E_x^*) \quad (11)$$

where ε is the laminate strain at delamination onset, t is the laminate thickness, E_x^0 is the undamaged laminate stiffness and E_x^* is the completely delaminated laminate stiffness. In his formula, the effect of matrix crack can not be taken into account because the matrix cracking has weak effect on the stiffness reduction of the CFRP laminate[6]. However, his model encountered the difficulty when it's applied to the edge delamination test of the GFRP composites because of the significant influence of matrix crack on the laminate stiffness reduction[12]. As shown in Fig.4, before edge delamination initiates, matrix cracks have a big number and they cause the nonlinear stress-strain curve for the GFRP laminate. If eq.(2) is used to get the fracture toughness of edge delamination, the contribution of matrix crack will be included so we cannot use this empirical global method to obtain the nonlinear fracture toughness. In our recent studies, the energy release rate of the pure edge delamination is obtained and the matrix crack effect can be reduced[12]

$$G_d = \frac{\varepsilon^2 t}{2} (E_x^c(D) - E_x^*(D)) \quad (12)$$

where $E_x^c(D)$ is the laminate stiffness at delamination onset with matrix crack density D in the off-axial plies and can be measured in experiment. The main difference of the two methods comes from the E_x^0 and $E_x^c(D)$. It leads to smaller value of the delamination fracture toughness in our result because the laminate stiffness at delamination onset is generally smaller than the undamaged laminate stiffness while the completely delaminated laminate stiffness is approximately equivalent for two different expressions. It shows that our method can reduce the matrix crack effect but either O'Brien's method or Liebowitz's method includes contributions of both edge delamination and matrix crack to fracture toughness, thus our result can be concluded to be smaller as shown in Table 1. Experimental studies show the matrix crack doesn't appear in the laminate only with a central 90° ply before edge delamination initiates, so this kind of laminate is recommended as the EDT specimen to eliminate the matrix crack effect.

Table 1 · Comparisons on the Mixed-mode Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

Material and Layup	T300 / QY8911 [± 30 ₂ / 90 / 90] _s	T300 / QY8911 [± 30 ₂ / 90] _s	S2 / QY8911 [± 30 ₂ / 90 / 90] _s	S2 / QY8911 [± 45 / 0 / 90] _s
O'Brien's Method	273	279	216	576
Present Method	256	279	171	291
Difference	6%	0%	21%	50%

After we understand the exact meaning of the parameter used in characterization of the mixed-mode fracture toughness of edge delamination, another test method is recommended. Formerly, the modulus of the completely delaminated laminate is computed by the lamination theory and rule of mixture, it's not measured by experiment[6]. So it's different from mode I and II fracture toughness characterizations, the obtained mixed-mode fracture toughness is neither a computed parameter nor an experimental value. The reason is the obscured meaning of the completely delaminated laminate modulus, it should be an experimental value but it's difficult to get by the former test, because final laminate fracture may occur before the edge delamination passes through the whole laminate width. So we recommend using such a procedure to measure this value: as soon as delamination occurs, a wedge is employed to force more delamination until the edge delamination passes through the laminate width as shown in Fig.5, then we may measure the laminate modulus, and use this value in eq.(12).

4. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, some nonlinear behaviour which affects the characterization of interlaminar fracture toughnesses and the modified data-reduction method and test procedure discussed in this paper are listed as followings:

On the DCB mode I test, they are: (1) Fiber bridging. Its effect on the fracture toughness is significant so we must employ the measured data of the specimen without fibre bridging effect. (2) Large deflection. A simple correction method in polynomial form is introduced to express the nonlinear effect. Berry's data-reduction method is still applicable if the deflection is not very large.

On the ENF mode II test, these effects should be noticed:(1) Microcrack and plastic deformation, their effects to nonlinear P-δ curve and fracture toughness are considerable. The microcrack effect should be eliminated. (2) Large deflection. But its effect is very small for the generally used typical ENF specimen with current materials.

On the EDT mixed-mode test, the matrix crack effect should be eliminated in data-reduction. A proposed procedure to measure the Young's modulus of the completely delaminated laminate is introduced and the laminate with the smallest thickness of the central 90° plies is recommended.

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Fig.1 Comparison of the exact and approximate correction factors of the fracture toughness F_G

Fig.2 Effect of fiber bridging to the fracture toughness

Fig.3 Variance of the large deflection correction factor of the typical thin ENF specimen

Fig.4 Stress-strain curves of the edge delamination specimens with and without matrix crack effect

Fig.5 Recommended test procedure of the EDT test